

PANCASILA STUDENT PROFILE MANAGEMENT IN BUILDING STUDENT CHARACTER

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Abstract

The Pancasila profile has a very important role in forming the character of students. The type of research used is a literature review, namely describing the role of the Pancasila profile on the character of students in elementary schools. The data collection model used is literature study. The results found are that in implementing the Pancasila Student Profile which consists of having faith, being devoted to God Almighty and having noble character, global diversity, independence, mutual cooperation, critical reasoning and creativity, where this really supports the development of students at this time. This is in the field of education which continues to develop. The aim of this research is to describe the planning, organization, implementation and supervision of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile in developing student character. This research uses qualitative research methods with a descriptive format. The results of this research show that the planning process for implementing the Pancasila student profile in developing student character is carried out by creating a curriculum program that includes intracurricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities. It is planned to include the P5 program (Project for Strengthening the Profile of Pancasila Students) which consists of six dimensions. In the process of organizing the implementation of the Pancasila student profile, the school principal creates an organizational structure and division of duties as project facilitator and coordinator. In implementing P5, teachers create teaching modules that cover six dimensions of Pancasila values. Meanwhile, monitoring the implementation of the Pancasila student profile is carried out by providing a special report card related to P5 which is given once a year.

Keywords: Pancasila Student Profile, Character.

A. INTRODUCTION

Education as a civilizing process is not only oriented towards developing good individuals, but also a good society." As a civilizing process, education needs to be dual-oriented, developing students who are able to understand themselves as well as their environment. This orientation must be balanced, where education helps individuals to recognize their potential, and provides each individual with the opportunity to place their own strengths in the surrounding environment. So education for cultivation requires the development of thinking power, feeling power, creative power and physical power. Character education through the application of Pancasila, so that students can have an inspiration that can be applied in everyday life. The Pancasila Student Profile is not only applied in certain subjects, but the Pancasila Student Profile is taught in all aspects contained in every subject taught at school. The importance of creating a Pancasila Student Profile is that it can provide students with the ability to have character in accordance with what is

contained in the Pancasila precepts in the Pancasila Student Profile. According to Ki Hadjar Dewantara, character education can be achieved using the Tricentre System, namely three social places that become educational centers. In children's lives there are three social places which are very important educational centers for them, namely the family world, the college world and the youth movement world. First, education will be perfect if it is not only based on the attitude and energy of the educator, but must also be accompanied by an atmosphere that is in accordance with the purpose of education. Then secondly, namely animating, increasing and encouraging feelings of sociality, it will not be realized if it is not preceded by self-education (individual education) because this is the basis of character education which will be able to give rise to a sense of community and a sense of sociality. Not all of education can make a significant contribution in developing abilities and forming dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the nation's life, especially in developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic citizens. And responsible. Problems arise with changes in this era, namely the decline in the character of the younger generation which is increasingly worrying because they are considered to be deviating far from the values that live in Indonesia. The various problems of juvenile delinquency are closely related to how character education in a school institution takes place, showing that there are many strategies that can be implemented in Asian countries, including Indonesia, including curriculum reform and other policies that strengthen the principles of equality and social justice. This recommendation is in line with the nation's ideals contained in Pancasila, namely social justice for the entire Indonesian nation. In other words, being oriented towards global goals is in no way contradictory to education to advance the nation's noble values and culture, with the Pancasila philosophy which is oriented towards human values as well as welfare and social justice.

The Pancasila student profile has six main characteristics, namely: "Faith, devotion to God Almighty, and noble character, Global diversity, Working together, Independent, Reasoning critically and Creatively" (Permendikbud No. 22 of 2020 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2020 -2024) . Character education can be interpreted as values education, character education, moral education, character education (Arifudin, 2022). In other words, character education is an essential part of the educational process, interpreted as a system of instilling character values in school members which includes the components of knowledge, awareness or will and action to implement these values, both towards God Almighty, oneself, fellow human beings, the environment, and nationality so that we become human beings. The current decline in the character of the nation's children is characterized by the weak character of students. There are still students who do not have honest, independent characteristics, are not polite towards parents and teachers, like to fight, cheat, are lazy about studying, prefer to play games, do not have a sense of discipline and responsibility in carrying out their obligations of worship towards the Creator and cannot work together/ collaborate with friends.

The general objective of this research is to determine the Profile Management of Pancasila students in developing student character. Meanwhile, the specific aim is to get an overview and analyze:

1. Planning for the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in SDN Bandung City.
2. Organizing the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in the City of Bandung.
3. Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in the City of Bandung.
4. Supervision of the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in SDN Bandung City.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

Based on the research problem regarding the Pancasila student profile in developing student character, the participants or data sources in this research are school principals, teachers and students. The data collection technique used in this research is through interviews and documentation studies. This research uses a literature review approach, which is a technique for proving or approaching a particular problem or it could be said that literature review is a scientific process that produces output in the form of a report that is intended to conduct scientific research or focus a study. Research with a literature review aims to inform readers of the results of other research that is closely related to the research to be carried out. Literature reviews contain reviews, summaries and the author's thoughts about several library sources (articles, books, slides, information from the internet, image and graphic data, etc.) about the topics discussed (Saputro, et al. 2021). This literature study aims to determine the influence and role of the Pancasila student profile in shaping the character of elementary school students. Have faith, have devotion to God Almighty, and have noble morals. Indonesian students are students who have faith and devotion to God Almighty and have noble morals, as mandated in the National Education System Law. This dimension is in line with the religious values that have been developed in Strengthening Character Education, where the content includes the individual's relationship with God, the individual with others and the individual with the universe. Indonesian students believe in the existence of God. Students who have faith, are devoted to God Almighty, and have noble morals are students who have morals in their relationship with God Almighty. He knows religious teachings and beliefs and uses this knowledge in everyday life. Pancasila students understand the meaning of morality, social justice, spirituality, have a love of religion, humans and nature. There are five main elements of faith, devotion to God Almighty, and good morals: (a) religious morals; (b) personal morals; (c) morals towards humans; (d) morals towards nature; and (e) state morals. Supporting documents obtained by researchers are in the form of teacher teaching administration. Apart from that, researchers also use triangulation techniques, namely data collection techniques that combine various existing techniques and data

sources, using source triangulation, namely collecting data from one informant to another informant who is also involved in the implementation of the Pancasila student profile in developing student character.

After obtaining field data, data analysis was carried out with the aim of finding important things that were studied and understood to answer research questions and formulate research conclusions. The data analysis technique used in this research is the Miles & Huberman model of data analysis (Sugiyono, 2016, pp. 337-345). These include, 1) data reduction, namely the process of summarizing data and selecting the main and important things; 2) data presentation (data display) in the form of short narrative descriptions; and 3) drawing conclusions (conclusion drawing) from research results that can answer the problem formulation so that implications and suggestions can be obtained that can be used by related parties. Researchers act as instruments and data collectors in qualitative research, which is one of its characteristics. Apart from people, there are other instruments that can be used (such as questionnaires, interview guides, observation guides, and so on), but their use is limited to helping researchers in their work as the main.

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pancasila Student Profile Management is a vision of the character and abilities of students in Indonesia. Pancasila students have a profile as "Indonesian students are lifelong learners who have global competence and behave in accordance with Pancasila values." Characteristics of students is one of the variables in learning design which is usually defined as the background experience possessed by students including aspects-other aspects of themselves such as general abilities, expectations for learning and students' physical and emotional characteristics that have an impact on learning effectiveness :

1. Planning for the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in SDN Bandung

Planning for the implementation of the Pancasila student profile in developing student character at SDN 152 Cigagak, Bandung city was carried out by creating a RKS work program created by the Curriculum Development Team consisting of the principal, Curriculum PKs and teachers. The RKS contains a plan for 8 national education standards consisting of content standards, graduation standards, process standards, assessment standards, standards for educators and education personnel, facilities and infrastructure standards, management standards and financing standards. The content standards contain curriculum programs consisting of KOSP and KTSP. Because at SDN 152 classes 1,2, 4 and 5 already use the Merdeka curriculum, while for classes 3 and 6 they still use Curriculum 13

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2. Organizing the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character at SDN Bandung City.

The Pancasila student profile is found in the Merdeka curriculum. However, an effort to implement the Pancasila student profile as a whole was carried out at SDN 152. The organization of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile was carried out by creating a curriculum program in addition to classroom learning, apart from that it was implemented in P5 activities (Strengthening the Pancasila Student Profile Project) . Pks Curriculum together with SDN 152 teachers created a P5 project whose theme was adapted to school conditions. In each theme of this project, each has a teaching module which aims to develop the character of students.

3. Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in SDN Bandung City.

The values contained in the Pancasila student profile are faith and devotion to God Almighty and noble character, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical reasoning and creativity. The following is an explanation of each of the Pancasila student profile values, namely:

- 1) Have faith, be devoted to God Almighty and have noble character. As a country based on Pancasila values, Indonesian citizens, including Indonesian students, are obliged to believe and laugh at God Almighty in accordance with their respective religions and beliefs. Faith is a vehicle for someone to achieve piety. Without faith it is impossible for a person to achieve piety, whereas piety is a person's ability to carry out all God's commands and avoid all His prohibitions. The key elements in having faith, being devoted to God Almighty and having noble morals are: Morals in religion; Personal morals; Morals towards fellow human beings; Morals towards nature; Morals in the state; Global Diversity. Makarim said that global diversity is a feeling of respect for diversity. This means that global diversity is an attitude of tolerance towards all existing differences. The key elements in global diversity are: Recognizing and appreciating various existing cultures; Intercultural communication skills in interacting with others; Reflection and responsibility for the experience of diversity.
- 2) Gotong royong as a profile of Pancasila students, will direct students to become social creatures who have the humility to help each other. The value of mutual cooperation teaches students to empathize with other humans. Applying the value of mutual cooperation from an early age will create a habit for students in their daily lives, in the environment where they live and even in the environment where they will work later. The aim of cultivating character from an early age is so that students are able to work with other people, build relationships in teams and work together to achieve certain goals. Students in Indonesia hold the nature of mutual cooperation within themselves, because with mutual cooperation they can solve problems together. The key elements in mutual cooperation are: Collaboration; Concern; Share.
- 3) Global Diversity Indonesia is a diverse country in terms of ethnicity, ethnicity, language, religion and belief, as well as other identity groups and social classes, including gender,

occupation and social economic status. Indonesian students, as part of this diversity, realize that diversity is a reality of life that cannot be avoided. Diversity in this context is the collection of knowledge and skills possessed by Indonesian students regarding the existence of self, group, culture, in a pluralistic local and global environment. Global diversity 4184 Journal on Education, Volume 05, No. 02, January-February 2023, pp. 4179-4188 is a sense of respect for diversity and tolerance for differences. This means being able to accept differences, without feeling judged, without feeling judgmental, or feeling like oneself and one's group are better than other groups. Not only on the Indonesian scale, as their country, but also on the world scale.

- 4) Independent, If previously students were required to be able to work together, then students also need to balance this by cultivating a sense of independence to continue to believe in themselves that they are capable of doing it first, and if they encounter obstacles they can ask others for help. The key elements in independence are: Awareness of oneself and the situation at hand and Self-Regulation.
- 5) Critical Reasoning is part of the process of evaluating evidence collected in solving problems or results produced through creative thinking (Widodo, 2016). Critical reasoning is a method of reasoning about any matter, substance, or problem, where students improve the quality of their reasoning by skillfully handling the structures inherent in their reasoning and applying intellectual standards to students. The key elements of critical reasoning are: Obtaining and processing existing information and ideas; Analyze and evaluate reasoning; Reflecting on thoughts and thought processes
- 6) Creative, creative thinking is a thinking process that generates new ideas and questions, tries various alternative choices and evaluates ideas using one's imagination. Students in Indonesia are also required to be able to modify and produce something original that is positive, meaningful, useful and has an impact both on themselves and others. The key elements of creativity are: Generating original ideas and Producing original work and actions.

The implementation of the Pancasila student profile in an effort to develop student character is also implemented in every P5 project which is carried out once a semester. In this P5 activity, students are not only given knowledge in the cognitive domain, but affective and psychomotor skills are also assessed by the teacher.

Students learn to collaborate with their friends regarding the values of faith, devotion to God Almighty and noble character, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical and creative reasoning. In this P5 project, it is not only the product or final result that is assessed, but rather the process of making the project. So it can be seen which characters have been achieved by students.

The theme of the P5 project at SDN 152 Cigagak, Bandung City consists of sustainable lifestyle, local wisdom and Bhinneka Tunggal Ika.

4. Supervision of the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile in Building Student Character in SDN Bandung City.

Supervision of the implementation of the Pancasila student profile in developing student character is carried out through a process of reflection and follow-up carried out by the principal and teachers in a fair, transparent and sustainable manner. In the differentiated learning process carried out by the teacher, the principal carries out clinical supervision and academic supervision to determine the extent to which the teacher carries out the learning process and the assessment process for students during class.

Meanwhile, for P5 (Pancasila Profile Strengthening Project) the school principal reflects at the end of each P5 activity in every official meeting. In reporting on the implementation of the Pancasila student profile in developing student character, every year students are given a P5 report card which contains an assessment of the character achievements that have been achieved by the students.

D. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusions of this research show that the Pancasila Student Profile is a formulation of national educational ideals as well as a synthesis of various references including the results of studies in Indonesia and also at the international level.

The Pancasila Student Profile is the answer to the question, what are the characteristics of Indonesian students, and the answer is summarized in the statement: "Indonesian students are lifelong students who are competent, have character and behave in accordance with Pancasila values. Such Indonesian students are students who have 6 dimensions that are developed optimally and in balance. These six dimensions are: 1) faith, devotion to God Almighty, and noble character, 2) global diversity, 3) working together, 4) independence, 5) critical reasoning, and 6) creativity.

As an effort to strengthen the development of the Pancasila Student Profile in schools, curriculum structure arrangements need to be expanded, not only regulating intracurricular programs but also co-curricular and extra-curricular programs. Co-curricular programs that are carried out outside the classroom and are not as formal as intra-curricular activities have the potential to build character and general competencies or global competencies contained in the Pancasila Student Profile.

It is hoped that the explanation of each dimension and its stages of development from phase to phase can help educators to design learning programs and activities that can optimize the development of character and competence as a whole and monitor the development of each student's profile.

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